

Additional Materials accompanying: ‘Modelling arterial pulse waves in healthy ageing’

This provides links to additional materials accompanying the following article:

[Charlton P.H., Mariscal Harana, J., Vennin, S., Li, Y., Chowienczyk, P. & Alastruey, J., “Modelling arterial pulse waves in healthy ageing: a database for in silico evaluation of haemodynamics and pulse wave indices,” *AJP Hear. Circ. Physiol.*, \[in press\], 2019.](#)

The Pulse Wave Database

The database of arterial pulse waves is available in comma-separated value (CSV), WaveForm DataBase (WFDB) and Matlab ® formats at <https://peterhcharlton.github.io/pwdb/> (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.2633174](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2633174)). The Database Manual is available at: <https://github.com/peterhcharlton/pwdb/wiki> .

Code for creating and analysing the Pulse Wave Database

The Matlab ® code used to create input files for simulations, and to collate and analyse the pulse wave database, are available at <https://peterhcharlton.github.io/pwdb/> (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.3271512](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3271512)). These include:

- [PulseAnalyse](https://peterhcharlton.github.io/pulse-analyse/), a signal processing tool for cardiovascular pulse waves, as detailed at <https://peterhcharlton.github.io/pulse-analyse/> (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.3272122](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3272122)).
- [AorticFlowWave](#), a script for creating aortic inflow waveforms.

Details of the code used to run the pulse wave simulations are available at <http://haemod.com/> , and access requests should be addressed to [J. Alastruey](#).

Instructions for replicating the study

Details of how to replicate this study are provided at <https://github.com/peterhcharlton/pwdb/wiki>.

The data collected during the literature review, and the Matlab ® code used to analyse these data, are available at <https://peterhcharlton.github.io/pwdb/> (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.3271512](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3271512)).

Further Information

Further information about the data and conditions of access can be found by emailing research.data@kcl.ac.uk. The authors can be contacted as detailed at <https://peterhcharlton.github.io/pwdb/contributions.html> .